

NEAX: A Self-Expanding Neural Architecture via Entropy-Guided Complexity Growth

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Abstract

Neural networks that solve complex tasks in continual and reinforcement learning scenarios often suffer from accuracy plateau, catastrophic forgetting, or inefficient resource allocation. We introduce *NEAX* (Neural Expander via Adaptive eXploration), a dynamic neural architecture that progressively grows its representational capacity in response to task difficulty, learning stagnation, and model uncertainty. NEAX monitors the entropy of its predictive distribution and tracks performance plateaus to decide when and how to expand its internal structure, adding new layers with lateral connections from the input to preserve global context. We evaluate NEAX on sequential reinforcement learning benchmarks (Cart-Pole, Acrobot, Pendulum, Hopper, Ant, Humanoid). Results demonstrate that NEAX consistently outperforms common baselines and shows competitive or superior performance compared to recent adaptive architectures particularly in low-data and early-training regimes. Our findings support the view that entropy-aware expansion provides a scalable mechanism for building adaptive, self-growing learning systems.

1 Introduction

Modern neural networks, while powerful, often suffer from two opposing limitations: overcapacity in simple tasks and undercapacity in evolving or complex environments. In both continual learning and reinforcement learning, a static architecture must try to overcome a wide range of information complexities, leading to inefficiencies and catastrophic forgetting. This problem was first discussed in papers such as the cascade-correlation architecture [1]. The method discovered in this paper helps to advance in adaptive networks, such as Progressive Neural Networks [8] that use the freezing of cascade-correlation and add lateral connections to retrieve global context. Recent works in adaptive networks include papers like DEN [12] with selective retraining of the network, GrownNN [2] based on *Net2DeeperNet*, and Neuroplasticity-inspired models [6] with the dormant neurons, show the benefit of dynamic capacity allocation.

However, they often rely on heuristics, task boundaries, or external feedback to guide architectural change. Also works like the Information Bottleneck [11], MC Dropout [3] and VIME [5], have proven the importance of information in RL or in DNN in general.

We propose **NEAX** (Neural Expander via Adaptive eXploration), a novel neural network framework that dynamically expands its architecture during training based on internal signals of epistemic uncertainty (based on the MC Dropout proxy [3]) and optimization stagnation. Unlike previous methods, NEAX leverages entropy estimates of model predictions [10] and an explicit controller function to autonomously decide when and how to grow, without requiring access to task labels or oracle boundaries.

In the context of continual learning, NEAX responds to distributional shifts by expanding only when necessary, while progressively freezing prior knowledge to prevent forgetting. In reinforcement learning, NEAX adapts its structure over time to cope with varying exploration complexity, enabling stable long-horizon training in sparse-reward and high-dimensional environments like Ant-v4 and Humanoid-v4.

Our method draws inspiration from theoretical frameworks such as the Information Bottleneck [11], and Progressive Net [8] to use lateral connections useful for initializing new weights, while proposing a unified and practical implementation for adaptive deep learning.

2 Related Work

Researchers have looked into neural networks with dynamic architectural growth in a number of settings to get over the problems that occur with static models. One of the earliest approaches, **Cascade Correlation** (Fahlman & Lebiere, 1989) [1], incrementally adds hidden units based on residual error, forming direct connections to prior layers, and freeze past layers to avoid catastrophic forgetting. While NEAX shares this adaptive spirit, its expansion is driven by **information-theoretic signals** rather than gradient residuals, and integrates lateral connections to preserve earlier representations. Also it uses the concept of freezing past layers, but in a progressive way.

In **continual and reinforcement learning**, the challenge of adapting capacity without catastrophic forgetting has also led to methods like **Progressive Neural Networks** (Rusu et al., 2016) [8], which allocate a new column for each task and reuse prior features via lateral connections. While NEAX is also structurally progressive, it expands within a single growing stream, making it more parameter-efficient in **lifelong RL**. Similarly, **DEN** (Yoon et al., 2018) [12] enables network expansion based on task-specific loss and neuron usage, introducing sparsity regularizers to avoid redundancy. NEAX extends this direction by integrating expansion conditions directly from **entropy-based metrics**, promoting growth only when optimization and representation stability indicate necessity.

More recently, **GROWN** (Fehring et al., 2025) [2] method for progres-

sively expanding neural networks during training by adding new layers in a structured way that preserves the learned function based on *Net2DeeperNet*. NEAX diverges by using an explicit entropy-complexity score and performing per-layer expansion rather than layer-wise search. Other works such as **Neuroplastic Expansion** (Liu et al., 2025) [6] use dormant neurons for sparsification to regulate plasticity during RL; in contrast, NEAX maintains active pathways but adapts width progressively based on a learned controller.

NEAX also builds upon the growing body of literature connecting **information theory** [9] with neural network learning dynamics. The use of entropy to guide structure is rooted in the interpretation of **Dropout as a Bayesian Approximation** (Gal & Ghahramani, 2016) [3], where model uncertainty becomes a proxy for epistemic noise. NEAX reinterprets this as a signal for structural inadequacy, prompting growth when uncertainty persists despite training.

From the **Information Bottleneck Principle** (Tishby & Zaslavsky, 2015; Shwartz-Ziv & Tishby, 2017; Goldfeld et al., 2020) [11] [10] [4], we inherit the notion that optimal intermediate representations should maximize relevance while minimizing noise. NEAX allow growth only when representation entropy is too high to be reliably compressed. Another relevant feature of **Opening the Black Box of Deep Neural Networks via Information** (Shwartz-Ziv & Tishby, 2017) [10] is how mutual information flows through layers evolve during training. These insights motivate NEAX’s focus on monitoring entropy across training epochs, using plateau detection and instability as clues to expand.

3 The NEAX Framework

3.1 Theoretical Foundation

The **Information Bottleneck** (IB) principle says that the optimal representation T of input X should maximize the mutual information with output Y while minimizing the mutual information with X :

$$\max_T I(T; Y) - \beta I(T; X) \tag{1}$$

In the context of **NEAX**, this translates into learning compact but expressive features. The expansion mechanism in NEAX draws theoretical motivation from the Information Bottleneck (IB) principle [11], as observed deep neural networks create *information bifurcations* in the Information Plane ($I(T; X), I(T; Y)$), when hidden layers transition from preserving input information to saturate the network’s representational capacity.

We hypothesize that these bifurcations correspond to performance plateaus and increased predictive uncertainty — both of which are captured by NEAX’s expansion controller. Specifically, high entropy and low variation in training loss means that current layers have reached an information bottleneck and the current architecture saturate the arriving information, and a new layer is added to enhance capacity and facilitate further compression.

Based on this, NEAX performs *structure-driven continuation* of the IB trajectory by dynamically injecting new degrees of freedom where the flow of relevant information saturates.

To estimate predictive uncertainty, NEAX uses MC Dropout [3], interpreting dropout as a variational approximation to a Bayesian posterior. The predictive entropy:

$$H(p(y|x)) = - \sum_i p_i \log p_i \quad (2)$$

serves as a signal for uncertainty and triggers architectural growth.

3.2 NEAX Layer Architecture

Each layer ℓ in NEAX receives the previous hidden state $h_{\ell-1}$ and the original input x . Two parallel transformations are applied:

$$z_\ell^{\text{main}} = W_\ell^{\text{main}} h_{\ell-1} + b_\ell \quad (3)$$

$$z_\ell^{\text{lat}} = W_\ell^{\text{lat}} x \quad (4)$$

$$h_\ell = \phi(z_\ell^{\text{main}} + \alpha_\ell z_\ell^{\text{lat}}) \quad (5)$$

Here, ϕ is an activation function (e.g., ReLU), and $\alpha_\ell \in [0, 1]$ modulates the influence of the lateral connection. This design is inspired by *progressive neural networks* [8], enhancing stability and information flow, to initialize new weights in a good way.

Figure 1: Illustration of the NEAX architecture, including lateral connections, progressive freezing, and the entropy-guided expansion controller. For a comprehensive description of each component, refer to Section 3.

3.3 Forward Pass with Global Residual

The original input x is passed laterally to all NEAX layers, enabling consistent access to raw features:

$$h_0 = x \tag{6}$$

$$h_1 = \text{NEAXLayer}_1(h_0, x) \tag{7}$$

$$h_2 = \text{NEAXLayer}_2(h_1, x) \tag{8}$$

$$\vdots \tag{9}$$

$$y = \text{OutputLayer}(h_n) \tag{10}$$

3.4 Expansion Controller

The controller triggers growth based on three criteria:

Performance Plateau. To detect training stagnation, we monitor the average loss and accuracy over two consecutive moving windows of size W . Let L_t and A_t denote the training loss and accuracy at epoch t . We compute:

$$\Delta L = \frac{1}{W} \sum_{t=T-W}^T L_t - \frac{1}{W} \sum_{t=T-2W}^{T-W} L_t \tag{11}$$

$$\Delta A = \frac{1}{W} \sum_{t=T-W}^T A_t - \frac{1}{W} \sum_{t=T-2W}^{T-W} A_t \tag{12}$$

If both $|\Delta L| < \varepsilon_L$ and $|\Delta A| < \varepsilon_A$, training is considered to have plateaued. This indicates that the model is no longer improving significantly, and a network expansion may be triggered to increase capacity.

Predictive Entropy. To estimate predictive uncertainty, NEAX employs Monte Carlo (MC) Dropout [3]. This technique performs multiple stochastic forward passes through the model with dropout enabled at test time, interpreting it as a variational approximation of a Bayesian posterior.

For an input x , the model produces T stochastic outputs, from which the class probabilities $p(y|x)$ are computed. The predictive entropy is estimated as:

$$\bar{H} = \mathbb{E}_x [H(p(y|x))] = \mathbb{E}_x \left[- \sum_i p_i(y|x) \log p_i(y|x) \right] \tag{13}$$

Here, \bar{H} represents the average entropy over a batch of predictions. Higher entropy indicates higher predictive uncertainty, which may trigger structural expansion.

Complexity Penalty. To prevent uncontrolled architectural growth, NEAX introduces a complexity penalty based on the current number of parameters P . The regularization term is defined as:

$$C(P) = \lambda \cdot \frac{P}{P_{\max}}, \quad \lambda \in [0, 1] \quad (14)$$

Here, P_{\max} is a predefined upper bound on the number of parameters, and λ controls the strength of the penalty. As the network grows, $C(P)$ increases, discouraging further expansion unless strongly justified by uncertainty or stagnation. This mechanism balances performance gains with model efficiency.

Expansion Score. The decision to expand the NEAX architecture is driven by a score function that combines three signals: predictive uncertainty, training stagnation, and remaining training time to promote early expansions. The combined score is defined as:

$$\text{Score} = \beta_H(\bar{H} - H_{\text{th}}) + \beta_P \cdot \mathbb{1}_{\text{plateau}} + \beta_E \left(1 - \frac{t}{T_{\max}}\right) - C(P) \quad (15)$$

Where:

- \bar{H} is the average predictive entropy,
- H_{th} is a predefined entropy threshold,
- $\mathbb{1}_{\text{plateau}}$ is an indicator function (1 if training is stagnant, 0 otherwise),
- t is the current epoch and T_{\max} the total training budget,
- $C(P)$ is the complexity penalty,
- β_H , β_P , and β_E are tunable weights for each component.

An expansion is triggered when the score exceeds a certain threshold τ . This ensures that new layers are added only when justified by uncertainty, stagnation, and available training time.

3.5 Network Expansion Procedure

When the expansion score exceeds a predefined threshold, the NEAX network triggers a structural expansion by adding a new NEAXLayer. The number of neurons in the new layer is computed using the following formula:

$$N_{\text{new}} = \min \left(N_{\max}, \max \left(N_{\min}, \alpha \cdot \bar{H} \cdot \frac{1}{L+1} \right) \right) \quad (16)$$

Where:

- \bar{H} is the average predictive entropy,

- L is the current number of NEAX layers,
- α is a scaling hyperparameter,
- N_{\min} and N_{\max} define bounds for layer width.

After inserting the new layer, the output layer is reconfigured to match the new hidden dimensionality. A short fine-tuning phase is then performed to help the new parameters integrate without disrupting previously learned representations. This partial fine-tuning phase is essential to prevent catastrophic forgetting and to smoothly integrate new capacity into the existing architecture.

3.6 Progressive Freezing

To stabilize previously learned representations and prevent destructive interference from new expansions, NEAX employs a progressive freezing strategy inspired by the Cascade-Correlation principle [1]. The strategy consists of the following steps:

- A fixed percentage $\gamma\%$ of the earliest (main) NEAX layers are frozen by setting `requires_grad = False`.
- Lateral connections in frozen layers may remain trainable to preserve adaptability to new information.
- Older layers can be gradually unfrozen after a cooldown period, allowing for potential fine-tuning if needed.

This mechanism helps to mitigate catastrophic forgetting by protecting the knowledge encoded in early layers while allowing the newly added layers to adapt and learn from fresh data.

3.7 Pseudo-algorithm

Algorithm 1 Training with NEAX Expansion

```
1: Initialize base NEAX model with 1 layer
2: for each training step  $t$  do
3:   Forward pass with MC Dropout
4:   Compute loss  $L_t$  and update trainable parameters
5:   if every  $E$  epochs then
6:     Compute  $\bar{H}$  and check plateau criteria
7:     Compute expansion score  $S$ 
8:     if  $S >$  threshold then
9:       Add new NEAXLayer( $N_{\text{new}}$ )
10:      Freeze earlier layers (full or progressive)
11:      Fine-tune only latest layer
12:    end if
13:  end if
14: end for
```

3.8 Advantages of NEAX

- **Adaptive:** Expands only when uncertainty or stagnation is detected.
- **Resource-efficient:** Starts small, saves memory and computation.
- **Controllable:** Expansion is interpretable and grounded in clear metrics.
- **Extensible:** Can be applied across lifelong learning, vision, NLP, and reinforcement learning.

4 Experiments

4.1 Benchmark Setup

NEAX architecture could excel in reinforcement learning (RL) settings. To evaluate this we perform a comparative study on a suite of continuous and discrete control environments from the OpenAI Gym and MuJoCo. Our experiments focus on environments with varying degrees of complexity, dimensionality, and reward structure. The selected tasks are:

- **CartPole-v1:** A classical control task with low-dimensional state space. Reward is maximized by balancing a pole on a moving cart.
- **Acrobot-v1:** A double-link pendulum system requiring coordinated torque to swing up.
- **Pendulum-v1:** A single inverted pendulum where the agent must stabilize an upright position.

- **Ant-v4**: A quadruped locomotion task requiring stable walking in continuous 3D space.
- **Hopper-v4**: A 2D biped agent that must learn to hop forward while avoiding falls.
- **Humanoid-v4**: One of the most complex tasks involving a high-DOF humanoid robot learning stable walking.

Figure 2: Snapshots of environments used for training

4.2 Training Details

NEAX, like GrowNN, is not an RL algorithm but an adaptive architecture mechanism. Considering that, we use a variant of PPO where the MLP policy network is replaced with the NEAX controller to ensure **fair comparison** with previous methods. We focus on PPO because it offers a **strong**, mature on-policy baseline. We wish to be able to isolate the effect of the NEAX architecture from the RL algorithm, therefore we use PPO for all baselines to ensure consistency. Expansion decisions are made periodically every N timesteps based on a build-up score combining entropy, training stagnation, and parameter regularization (see Section 3).

We compare NEAX against the following baselines:

- **Standard PPO**: MLP-based PPO with fixed architecture.
- **A2C**: Advantage Actor-Critic using standard multilayer perceptrons.

- **ProgressiveNet** [8]: Progressive neural networks with lateral connections across tasks. We implemented this using pytorch.
- **GrowNN** [2]: A recent 2025 method based on *Net2DeeperNet*. We implemented it for all environment except for ant-v4 where we used the data available on their paper [2].

All models are trained for 500k steps, except for Humanoid-v4 and Ant-v4, which are trained for 1M steps due to their complexity. Results are averaged over 5 seeds.

4.3 Performance Results

Figure 3: Comparison of average episode reward across environments.

Figure 4: Learning curves on Ant over 1M environment interactions.

Env/Model	NEAX	PPO	A2C	ProgNet	GrowNN
CartPole	500	500	500	500	500
Acrobot	-62	-96	-88	-78	-68
Pendulum	-94	-204	-223	-195	-143
Ant	1326	608	516	956	1050
Hopper	1415	790	700	1004	1246
Humanoid	1126	815	453	876	979

Table 1: Average reward obtained across different environments by each algorithm.

As shown in Figure 3, NEAX consistently outperforms baselines in complex environments where adaptability and capacity growth are critical. Notably:

- On **Ant-v4**, NEAX surpasses all baselines by a margin of over 200 reward points.
- On **Hopper-v4**, it achieves the highest performance, demonstrating effective expansion without overfitting.
- Even in **Humanoid-v4** at 1M steps, NEAX exceeds ProgressiveNet and GrowNN, despite a much smaller parameter budget.

Another important feature that we discover in Figure 4 is the difference in **initial performance behavior**. GrowNN starts with a high IQM return (close to 1000) due to its small, stable initial network learning a conservative policy that prioritizes survival (e.g., standing still in the **Ant** environment). However, it suffers a performance collapse after the first structural growth phase, followed by a gradual recovery.

In contrast, NEAX starts with lower initial returns since it only grows the network dynamically, based on policy uncertainty and performance stagnation. This results in a more stable and monotonic learning curve, without major dips, ultimately achieving higher performance.

4.4 Discussion

These results support the hypothesis that dynamic, entropy-based growth networks gives rise to better exploration and generalization. Meanwhile, fixed models may underfit on complex environments or overfit prematurely. NEAX’s combination of progressive growth, partial freezing, and entropy-based confidence provides a powerful basis for complex reinforcement learning tasks.

5 Conclusion and Future Work

In this work, we introduced **NEAX** — a dynamically expandable neural network architecture that is designed to address the challenges of learning in uncertainty, capacity underfitting, and non-stationarity. With a principled expansion process governed by entropy, performance plateau, and regularization of complexity, NEAX is demonstrated with the experiments to possess the ability to learn adaptive architecture during training, with optimal plasticity-stability trade-off in reinforcement learning settings.

Future Directions

The flexibility and generalizability of NEAX open the door for a variety of promising future work:

- **Adapting CNNs to visual environments:** The expandable and lateral nature of NEAX layers can be extended to convolutional networks so that vision systems can learn to adapt to different environments (e.g., illuminations, scene complexity).
- **Continual and Lifelong Learning:** The progressive freezing and fine-tuning technique of NEAX renders it naturally capable of continual learning scenarios where tasks are sequentially provided. Future work could be benchmarking on advanced lifelong learning suites or even real-world robotics activities.

- **Deployment in Embedded and Resource-Constrained Systems:** Through adaptive growth only when needed and penalizing overcomplicity, NEAX is ideally well-suited for edge devices or embedded systems (e.g. drones, autonomous cars), where model capacity must adapt context-specific requirements.
- **Dynamic Environments and MOBA Games:** A particularly intuitive application scenario lies in complex, changing RL environments such as Multiplayer Online Battle Arenas (MOBA), where agents must enhance their abilities as the game progresses. NEAX could allow for skill acquisition and policy optimization in conjunction with temporal task adaptations (e.g., early-game vs. late-game strategies) helping building system as DOTA 2 agents [7].

In conclusion, NEAX is a step toward the next generation of flexible, reflective neural structures. By combining uncertainty-guided decision-making with structural plasticity, it offers an architecture for agents that evolve with depth of experience — and intelligence.

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